

Strengthening research ethics committees in crises:

Why funding matters _____

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Strengthening research ethics committees in crises: Why funding matters

DOCUMENT INFORMATION

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Acknowledgements: Kate Chatfield and Doris Schroeder

Citing suggestion: Seedall, Carly, Jurate Lekstutiene, Agne Girkontaite, Vilma Lukaseviciene, Lisa Tambornino, Vygintas Aliukonis, and Eugenijus Gefenas (2025) Strengthening research ethics committees in crises: Why funding matters, a report for the PREPARED project, available at: <https://prepared-project.eu/>

Funded by the European Union. UK participants in Horizon Europe Project Prepared are supported by UK Research and Innovation grant number 10048353 (University of Central Lancashire). Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the Research Executive Agency or UKRI. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority nor UKRI can be held responsible for them.

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Executive Summary

Research ethics committees (RECs) played a key role in advancing ethical research during the COVID-19 pandemic. However, in a survey of 324 RECs in 80 countries across the globe, REC members and staff reported facing significant challenges related to the ethical reviews of protocols. Our study shows that these challenges can be linked to a lack of funding for RECs. **We therefore call on key financial supporters of RECs – especially institutional leaders and policymakers – to provide stable funding for RECs before the occurrence of the next crisis.**

Role of RECs and challenges faced in global crises

RECs play a crucial role in enabling research to respond effectively to global crises while safeguarding ethical standards. In times of crisis, there is often pressure to act quickly — but ethical oversight ensures that urgency does not override responsibility. As Hellmann et al. (2020) argue, the complex challenges of crises require us to “think first, act better later” — a principle that RECs help operationalise by ensuring that research responses are carefully considered, ethically sound, and socially responsible. ³

During the COVID-19 pandemic, demand for REC reviews increased significantly. In the qualitative results, RECs widely reported a surge in protocol submissions related to COVID-19, along with widespread pressure to expedite the review process. As a result, **79% (n= 256) of RECs faced significant challenges**, a trend observed across continents and REC structures.

REC challenges faced during the pandemic

³ Hellmann, F., Cardoso Bittencourt, S., Stolf Brzozowski, F., Finkler, M., Verdi, M., & Caponi, S. (2020, May 25). COVID-19: Think First, act better later. *Bioethics Today*. <https://bioethicstoday.org/blog/covid-19-think-first-act-better-later/>

When asked about the most significant challenges they faced, the most reported challenges included **the speed of reviews (57%), meeting participation (36%), and the monitoring of research protocols (30%).**

REC challenges faced during the pandemic*

*Respondents were asked to select all that applied.

** Other challenges cited in the qualitative results included the following: insufficient secretariat capacity, difficulties in finding available external experts – particularly clinicians on the front lines – a lack of technical support, and inadequate REC training for reviewing crisis-related research.

REC funding sources

RECs in our study are funded by their institutions (57%), national governments (24%), industry and the private sector (11%), and NGOs/INGOs (4%). **Institutional leaders and policymakers are thus the primary stakeholders responsible for ensuring that RECs receive adequate and sustainable funding.**

Self-reported funding sources of RECs*

*Some RECs reported more than one funding source.

Despite the importance of their work, over **22% of RECs reported that they are not compensated at all.**

Furthermore, funding availability was clearly associated with country income level: 28% of RECs based in low- or middle-income countries (LMICs) and 16% of RECs based in high-income countries (HICs) reported being unfunded. These figures demonstrate that **RECs in LMICs were significantly more likely to report having no funding than those in HICs, with approximately twice the likelihood of being unfunded.**⁴

⁴ Chi-squared test: $p = 0.018$; Fisher's Exact test: $p = 0.017$; Odds Ratio = 2.01, 95% CI: 1.12–3.67.

Adequacy of REC funding

RECs expressed concerns about the adequacy of their funding: **only 33.3% of RECs reported that their funding is either somewhat adequate or very adequate.**

Perception of funding adequacy among RECs*

Despite receiving some funding, most **RECs remain chronically underfunded**, with resources falling short of what is needed to support their work, according to our survey.

In the qualitative responses, several REC members noted disparities in compensation, stating that only chairs, secretariats, and external experts were typically paid for their review work, while regular members were not. Some explicitly described this as a source of perceived unfairness.

Several respondents in the qualitative responses also described REC work as a secondary responsibility alongside their main employment. Nonetheless, they characterised the review of research protocols as highly specialised, requiring considerable responsibility and expertise. Several respondents also noted that such work would typically be better compensated in other professional contexts, particularly during public health emergencies or crises.

Many qualitative respondents emphasised intrinsic motivation as a key driver of their continued participation, with some describing how they attended meetings and completed work outside of regular hours. While compensation was not viewed as the primary motivation, several respondents expressed a desire for their work to be formally recognised as a critical institutional activity that warrants appropriate support and resourcing.

REC preparedness for the COVID-19 pandemic

When asked if their RECs were prepared to review research during the COVID-19 pandemic (e.g., having adequate resources such as staffing, funding, and technology), 55% of RECs agreed or strongly agreed.

REC preparedness to review research during COVID-19*

*Percentages sum to 99% due to rounding.

However, funding plays a critical role in how prepared RECs were to face challenges during the pandemic: **funded RECs reported significantly higher perceptions of preparedness for the COVID-19 pandemic than unfunded RECs.**⁵ This suggests that adequate funding not only supports the operational capacity of RECs but also enhances their ability to respond effectively to urgent and complex research demands during crises.

⁵ T-test: $p = 0.001$, funded Mean = 3.52, unfunded Mean = 2.93; with additional support from non-parametric tests – Wilcoxon: $p = 0.0001$; Spearman: $\rho = -0.216$, $p < 0.0001$.

Impacts on challenges and quality of ethics reviews

Perceptions of funding adequacy are linked to the challenges RECs face during crises: RECs that considered their funding inadequate were significantly more likely to report difficulties during the COVID-19 pandemic.⁶

Funding may also play a role in review quality: RECs that reported their compensation as being adequate were less likely to indicate that the quality of their reviews was negatively impacted by the COVID-19 pandemic.⁷ However, even in under-resourced settings, some REC members were committed to maintaining high standards — often through personal sacrifice.

As one respondent reflected in the qualitative results:

“I am extremely proud of the work we did to facilitate expedited timelines for the most important research, and at no point did we compromise the quality or integrity of our reviews. We just worked twice as many hours.”

Most RECs (89%) did not receive additional monetary resources during the pandemic. However, those who did were not statistically more likely to feel prepared for the COVID-19 pandemic.⁸ Furthermore, in the qualitative results, RECs reported that shortages existed even before the pandemic and that the crisis only exacerbated the problem. **RECs should thus be adequately compensated during normal times**, before the next crisis emerges.

⁶ Chi-Square: $X^2 = 22.02$, $p = 0.0002$.

⁷ Spearman: $\rho = -0.122$, $p = 0.029$; Chi-Square: $X^2 = 9.69$, $p = 0.046$.

⁸ ANOVA: $p = 0.999$; Kruskal-Wallis: $p = 0.9732$; Spearman correlation: $\rho = -0.003$, $p = 0.9634$.

The influence of law & regulation

The funding of RECs is crucial not only from an ethical and practical standpoint but is also frequently anchored in legal frameworks. Many of the RECs surveyed reported that relevant laws or regulations – at the institutional, national, or regional level – govern the funding of their bodies. Moreover, **national funding, which is often legally mandated, was found to be associated with a higher perception of funding adequacy compared to other funding sources.**⁹ Therefore, policymakers should, where possible, ensure that funding mechanisms for RECs are firmly established within legal frameworks.

⁹ T-test: $p = 0.0136$, national funding Mean = 3.03, other funding Mean = 2.61; with additional support from non-parametric tests – Wilcoxon: $p = 0.0125$; Spearman: $\rho = 0.139$, $p = 0.0123$.

Monetary vs. non-monetary compensation

REC funding comes in many forms. Of RECs that were compensated, many reported receiving non-monetary forms of compensation, such as recognition (e.g., formal acknowledgement through titles, awards, or institutional communications; 39%), professional development opportunities (38%), and a reduction in other professional responsibilities (16%).

Importantly, **non-monetary compensation significantly improved RECs' perceptions of compensation adequacy**.¹⁰ RECs that received neither monetary nor non-monetary compensation were statistically more likely to perceive their compensation as inadequate.¹¹

Not all funding has to be monetary: policymakers and institutional leaders should thus **consider providing non-monetary forms of compensation to REC members**.

COMPENSATION TYPES

¹⁰ T-test: $p = 0.0050$, non-monetary compensation Mean = 3.00, no non-monetary compensation Mean = 2.57; with additional support from non-parametric tests – Wilcoxon: $p = 0.0049$; Spearman: $\rho = 0.156$, $p = 0.0048$.

¹¹ T-test: $p < 0.001$, unfunded Mean = 2.13, funded Mean = 2.89; Wilcoxon: $p = 0.00002$.

Determination of compensation

RECs reported that their compensation takes a number of different formats: 45% reported a per meeting or review stipend, where members receive a fixed amount for each review; 10% reported reimbursement of expenses, where members are compensated for travel, accommodation, and other necessary expenses; 8% reported an annual honorarium, where a set annual fee is provided regardless of the number of proposals at REC reviews; and 8% reported an hourly work rate. Others were not funded or noted other formats (34%).

Compensation formats

In the qualitative results, some RECs expressed that their payment systems were outdated, which further contributed to a sense of inequity.

Despite these challenges, however, the specific format of compensation did not appear to impact RECs' feelings of preparedness for the COVID-19 pandemic, nor did it influence their perceptions of the adequacy of their compensation.

Policymakers and institutional leaders should focus less on the specific format of compensation and more on **ensuring that any model used is fair, regularly updated, and reflective of RECs' evolving needs.**

Specific needs of RECs during crises

When asked to specify their resource needs, 50% of RECs reported a need for technological infrastructure, such as laptops and software for remote work; 41% reported a need for administrative support, including help with staffing and review coordination; 35% reported a need for training or guidance for ethics review body members; 16% reported a need for funds for the recruitment of new members; and 15% reported a need for funds for external advisors or consultants.

REC resource needs

In the qualitative findings, RECs that had access to adequate resources, particularly technological and administrative support, attributed their ability to maintain ethical standards efficiently to these resources. **Support for RECs may therefore be focused on addressing these key areas.**

Conclusion

RECs play an essential role in advancing research that is grounded in ethics, especially during global crises. Our survey findings point to the need for stable, adequate funding to support RECs in fulfilling their responsibilities, particularly in times of crisis. The COVID-19 pandemic demonstrated the challenges RECs face when funding is insufficient, resulting in delayed and lower-quality reviews as well as overburdened staff.

Policymakers, institutional leaders, and other stakeholders supporting RECs must take immediate action to ensure that these bodies receive the funding and resources they need to function effectively, both in times of normalcy and during emergencies. Specifically, we call for the following:

1. Stable, long-term funding. Governments, institutions, and donors should commit to sustainable funding models for RECs that are not only responsive to crises but also pre-emptively support RECs' operational capacity during non-crisis periods.

2. Fair and updated compensation models. Compensation systems should be regularly updated to account for inflation, cost-of-living increases, and the growing responsibility of REC members, particularly in the face of global crises.

3. Increased non-monetary support. Institutional leaders may consider providing non-monetary support to RECs, such as professional development, recognition, and reduced workloads in other areas.

4. Focus on critical resource areas. Funding and support should address the specific resource needs identified by RECs, such as technological infrastructure, administrative support, training for ethics review bodies, and funds for recruitment and expert consultations.

5. Legislative frameworks. Policymakers should anchor REC funding mechanisms within the law, ensuring that funding is consistent and reliable.

By taking these steps, it can be ensured that RECs are well-equipped to uphold the ethical standards of research and contribute to the successful resolution of global challenges. **RECs must not only be seen as essential to the research process but also be provided with the resources and recognition they need to support research effectively.**